

Polymer Light Emitting Diodes Based on DB-PPV/ZnO Nanocomposite

Emissive Layer

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Even after 20 years of extensive research attention, organic/polymer light emitting diodes (OLEDs/PLEDs) continue to generate considerable interest as potential candidates for use in flat panel displays and solid state lighting(1-4). They have some advantages such as low fabrication cost, easy processing, lightweight, and can be fabricated on large area display and flexible substrate etc.. However, the conjugated polymer is easily affected by the moisture and oxygen in the environment, and then influences the performance and life time to limit its applications in commercial, so there are many researchers discussing to improve the performance of PLED.

We fabricated a polymer light emitting diode single layer structure that had been made ITO/PEDOT:PSS/DB-PPV-ZnO/Ca/Al. We observed that the roughness of the emission layer increased when the ZnO nanoparticle composite with the proportion of ZnO nanoparticles increased. The surface morphologies of the polymers were measured by AFM and SEM. The J-V and L-I characteristics indicate that the addition of ZnO nanoparticles can facilitate electrical injection and charge transport. It demonstrated that ZnO nanoparticles have the ability to improve the current density, luminance and efficiency. After being annealed, the nanocomposite device at 120°C, the highest luminance efficiency is 2.90 cd/A(5-6).

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